

THEORETICAL STUDY TO DETERMINE (INTER-) DEPENDENCY OF VARIABLES FUNCTIONING TO PROMOTION AND SALES IN BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

Reflection of marketing effort, media and communication, is often indicated by magnitude and scale-effect of revenue or profit. It is a marketer's strong task to create and make a sustainable and competitive marketing effort by various promotion interaction programmes using media communications such as advertising, etc. Interaction, by persuasion indeed, between promotion (P) and selling (S), takes the bond of marketing and its management. Without promotion, selling is utterly impossible. P must always be there prior to every S. The study of research interest has explained several dimensions of P-S interaction symbiosis and several marketing possibilities of it through applying methodology of innovation interests, to formulate a service performance modelling. Result of this modelling, as outcome of innovation also, would include dynamic and mobile nature of interaction symbiosis. Various scopes with respect to all kinds of marketing benefits to marketer and research interests to researcher are at every pace of this methodological study.

Keywords: Marketing Communication Programme, Physical Producing, Proposition Marketing, Promotion-Sales Symbiosis, Service performance model.

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INTRODUCTION

Marketing management is the division in an organization in which one of several links (that play with organization's fulfillment) is interaction between promotion and selling. In any marketing communication programme, marketer does the right thing as per his/her visionary 'marketing' fulfillment. To sell a proposition, be it product or service, marketer should always avoid ways having risk perceptions than taking stable and competitive paths to be of less risky and with secured 'proposition line' strategy in marketing^[1]. In doing this, marketing operation takes basic stages like advertisement, supply chain, promotion, personal selling, etc. of marketing to assure the strategy to be to be the best enough in the market or industry^[2]. Brand management which is also a part of various promotional events still lacks with its promotional permit to everywhere use due to its inability of 'off-setting'. So, marketer remains with very careful mindset and strategies while dealing with promotional activities.

Promoting a proposition becomes an inevitable part of marketing management, especially in now-a-days marketing of selling and value. Promotional or simply 'Promotion' covers entire spread of the propositional acquaintances to its target market/goals. Promotion basically includes both print and digital media coverage^[3]. Revenue of proposition marketing depends on budget reimbursed for the promotion and it (budget) should not be out of the budget as decided by an organization's objectives.

Each of activities of proposition promotion is with a target that it would create the 'persuasive' effort (than only selling), on overall basis, onto the customer to make a purchase decision at its ultimatum. Purchasing a proposition of marketer or selling a proposition by the marketer which 'directly' creates the flow of coins as the output revenue may be termed as the 'rational' or 'practical' selling of the proposition marketing.

Figure 1: Zone, actual and influencing, of promotion marketing in business management

But, it is not always a customary event for a promotion to cause its selling as the irresistible happening^[4]. For a promotion effort of proposition, its selling mayor may not happen and is quite uncertain also.

After a long history of marketing management, it is now the tradition that with the attempt (of persuasion creation) as marketer’s target, all the promotional activity must go along accordingly and get set with the marketer’s plan to the marketing obviously but the dependency on the rational selling (as to the direct outcome) would remain only as optional^[5, 12]. It is because of the fact that today’s uncertainty is not the cause marketer should rely upon by his/her promotional programme.

Figure 2: Basic interaction of promotion to sale (P – S; proposition: on successful)

Therefore Promotion (P) or Selling (S) programme of a proposition is to be equal to:

Rational (Direct) P or S + Persuasion (Indirect) P or S

= Direct marketing + Indirect marketing . . . (Eq. B1)

Eq. B1 is only for an expressive interest of the study, though it considers research scopes so far as this study concludes with.

Leadership usually gets enhanced by a strategic ‘promotional’ marketing. As there is lesser capacity to offset any losses, any promotional endeavors should be taken care with great seriousness, to a marketer. So, there is a need to make and establish a ‘stable’ sales strategy alongwith ‘profitable’ visionary. This study has given the thought to do research to find out ‘intrigue’ layers in the interaction relationship between P and S. Figure 1 shows the basic of such discussion wherein an interaction is said to take place once promotion (P) is applied and given into a proposition.

Figure 3: Basic fundamental of sale to promotion (S – P; proposition: on unsuccessful)

Considering persuasion as the promotional objective (both short term and long-term), the diagram, Figure 1, gives the concept of ability of persuasion to create a far-reaching selling prospect from its ‘core’ sales prospect.

Figure 4: Cyclic “continuous” process of promotion–sale interaction

(Proposition on “continuous” and “cyclic” purchasing effort)

Boundaries, like PPB and SPB, that are assumed always to be there in any promotional programme define the possibility and assurance of having the promotional prospects to go into and create a good/better prospect of selling/profitability. These boundaries have been become so well in the discussion afterwards that it would provide a better insight to investigate the relationship (P-S) more correctly. The boundaries and their intermediate presences is altogether an asset to an organization’s goals indeed and is well observed by this research study by finding out ‘intermediate’ phenomena (so occurred) in an interaction relationship (between P and S) in propositional marketing and businesses. The term ‘indirect marketing’ is included which defines such persuasions that are only long-term (that is, not as active as the ‘direct’ one) by nature to cause the result to profit/the selling. It is found by the study that indirect marketing though market (or proposition) specific does create the better possibility to generate sales growth.

Distinguishing between direct and indirect marketing is better observed when a proposition by P is sold immediately or not by so lately (Figure 2) and when a further P is required or needed after selling prospect (led by P usually indeed) is failed (Figure 3).

Now it is quite clear of a fact that accuracy level of a promotional programme tells the end-level efficacy by sales and profitable output. There must thereby be pruning of promotions to entail a specific and certain selling outcome and in order to do this, a visionary approach becomes essential to a marketer in the persuasion strategy. Failure may happen to reach at a certain sale level but there should be the 'clear' strategic outlines by the interaction and its anticipating reactive natures so far as by the market^[6].

Figure 5: The Interaction Model (Transformation of continuous interaction)

It is, in common way of occurrence, observed as a challenge between the part 'promotion' and its 'selling' of marketing business management programme. These two operations are consequent (Figure 4) to each other and provide 'credit' on both ways to one on other; if selling is good or excellent, it is thought that the promotion was quite to be of 'good' nature in the marketing efforts; conversely, if the promotion is likely considered as good or excellent, then the selling operation is expected to be giving better results (Figure 1 and Figure 2). So, in a common parlance, whatsoever the marketing programme may be, in marketing a proposition in business^[7], a process comes to an observance that an interaction takes place between P and S; continuously and repeatedly, on the initiation of P (Figure 5). It is assumed that interaction of proposition 'initiates' and starts from P, not from S.

Table 1: Of interaction, cyclic process operation and needs of P

Issue	Cycle definition	Cycle in number	Sales history	Cycle description	P's requirement [^]
P-S interaction	One Cycle = Single rotation (get back) from S to P on failure to 'desired' S = Following + Leading	1 st Cycle	Dissatisfied Sales.	Promotion (to be repeated, with same or varying magnitude).	1st Cycle P + Starter P [^]
		2 nd Cycle	Improved sales, but still is demanding P to repeat.	Comparative cyclic dominance between P and S.	2nd Cycle P + Starter P
		3 rd Cycle	Improved sales, but is demanding more P's to repeat.	Comparative cyclic dominance between P and S.	3rd Cycle P + Starter P
	
		n-th Cycle	Satisfied sales, and not demanding further P to repeat.	Successful dominance between Promotion and Sales.	n-th Cycle P + Starter P

[^]the first P that initiates and begins the operation process (as the direct also) is here called as starter P into the interaction process.

Due to repetitive nature of the process, cyclic rotations would be there in the interaction between P and S. Selling is a tough instance to occur so quite in an obvious manner prevalence of indirect marketing is often observed in market/business and it is uncertain to pre-determine any cycle as the cycle for ‘final’ selling. Table 1 shows it with explanation of sales history by level of the interaction and needs to supply P (to the interaction) to fulfill S.

Table 2: Transformation Variables

Transformation Cycle [^]	Functional Variable	Description
Following	P based (that is, by promotional programme as decided by a marketer for his/her organization)	Screened ‘promotion’ variables; Usually one-half cycle in interaction (forward)
Leading	Porter’s five forces, economic environment, change strategies, etc. (in addition to and a combination of factors of both S and P)	Raw selection variables; Usually one-half cycle in interaction (backward)

[^]Following is more refined than leading transformation by variables selection and by leading transformation.

There should be a war, in consequence, of comparative strengths between available level of S and its ‘desirous’ want against availability of P. This war is to arrive at a ‘desired’ S ultimately. Any cycle that forms in this of S to P (or, P to S) process must have a birth and a death within the process (Figure 5).

Table 3: Interaction Between Promotion and Selling[^]

Cycle In Process	Proposition Result	Least No. Of Frequency ^{^^}	Organizational Management / Marketing Result
P-S (P to S)	Successful	= 0	Excellent
S-P (S to P)	Not successful/Unsuccessful	= 1	not Excellent even though Good and Improving
P-S-P	Continuous; Not unsuccessful ^{^^^}	> 1	neither Excellent nor Good/Improving, but a ‘desired’ and persuasive ‘value’ marketing

[^]see Figure 5.

^{^^}proposition marketing is said to be successful once S is reached and stable at the ‘desired’ S.

^{^^^}P is to be a function of having ‘off-setting’ ability to organizational goals.

Each cyclic characteristic must be different than other cycles, ever, in the rotation. However, there are two types of transformation observed to be found in a cycle –

- Leading transformation cycle (backward moving).
- Following transformation cycle (forward moving).

Promotions (P) should always be acting on each transformation type in a cycle (Table 2), though there could be several other ‘associated’ variables as functional to P (and also S) as applicable in an interaction function/cycle. Operation/cyclic strength should be about the satisfaction level (Table 3) which, in turn, indicates ‘frequency’ level which is also representative of the cycle.

So, the entire process of P to the S transformation would create the cyclic sequences like P-S-P, S-P-S, etc. again and again in a process system of proposition marketing and it’s like music CD/DVD player (Figure 4) which plays continuously till stoppage is given. So, it is ‘continuous’ as for its basic fundamental of construction to achieve business goals.

From this research, it becomes the conclusive outcome to know and determine how a selling operation could be made and should be prepared of, in consequence of the P indeed, into building a firm a ‘better’ stage of the proposition selling. Noted here that there should be categories of promotional activities, under P, that not only do include advertising, branding, etc.

but also other several inclusive like social reputation/image, market dominance, industry value, etc. of an organization. So, in an interaction P always plays the role of initiator to begin P-S process.

Propositions are always targeted by such marketing management/programme that results to a 'desired' selling or profitability by minimum frequency, shorter cyclic intervals and correct programme set^{[8], [9]}. In cases of higher/more frequency, intervals etc., marketing results may sound as inefficient and non-effective, unless preventative measures^[10] are not implemented. To situations, proposition (product/service) might be kept positioned on 'levels of frequency' to over long-staying for various reasons as follows:

- To complete a total set of various promotional activities.
- To collect as well as gather overall experience of proposition by all kinds of P's by nature.
- To have record of range of the exposures by marketing programme and its frequency results for marketing competitiveness/new proposition for future/other use.
- Not to underestimate the process model by limited sets of P's.
- To correct and become corrected by number of frequencies to 'desired' S and it may prove to economic finding.
- To determine a correct set of promotional activities for the 'selling' standard.
- To validate sets of P and S, of earlier promotions or experimentation or else.
- To utilise the proposition and/or market to its ultimate outcome ability (profit) by P-S interaction.
 - To test a promotion's strength based on proposition's value gathering/enhancing ability.
 - To determine layers of strength, in cycle, where promotion gives optimum result of profitability.

By this way of analysis and determinations, marketer could be able to correctly place proposition by considering facts about market, industry, environment (macro + micro), etc., thereby it would lead to give a better efficacy level to promotional programme which is considered as so careful as risky initiative to its organization.

'Promotional' Marketing Process Transforming Into 'Promotional' Model

Description process of Figure 5 and Table 2 forms basis of turning the process into a model. In the model, the cyclic process functions begin (from left to right and then right to left) continuously and repeatedly again and again till it achieves a satisfactory 'desired' sales level. Process should always start from P (promotion), as discussed. Here, one complete cycle is shown clearly by constituting it of P to S and S to P (Figure 5) as summation together. This type of the cycles would keep forming up continuously as long as selling is not satisfied to a 'desired' extent by a level or magnitude. This simplification of the repetitive (Fourier!) or cyclic process, on further elaboration and description has revealed it with forming as of like a model process that could be named as 'promotional' model (described in methodology afterwards; Figure 7). Moreover, there might have modifications/changes, in the (nodal) model variables determination, as the cycle continues as shown by Figure 5. The model signifies the respective dominance of P and S in an interaction 'marketing' programme. Once 'desired' or 'final' level of selling is achieved the model is concluded and said to done completely with all satisfaction of its promotional objective. However, with lots of modelling research scopes, the study would be successful if it has ended with a 'selling' placement in business that is of marketer-centric profitability and competitive indeed.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Following are the targets of the study entirely -

- To set out the benchmark to be achieved by the promotion segment of marketing by an organization.
- To describe marketing by promotion to align itself with the organization function/system by the model.
- To determine and establish a promotion-cum-selling scenario by best interaction outcome that it could provide the solutions of various crisis' facing condition of a marketer in 'proposition' marketing.
- To emphasis 'selling' at the same level of importance as that of 'promotion' in 'promotion directing to sales philosophy' to bring in an equilibrium in the process system of P-S interaction.
- To determine a cohesive model to negotiate through interaction 'P-S' alongwith its interaction outcomes as vivid as close to physicality of product/service.
- To keep up future research scopes in the discussion all along.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

In fulfilling marketing/proposition management scopes, various P-S interaction problems that may be suggested with could provide ways of better vision by their solutions^{[11], [12]}.

Basic aspects that are given due consideration in developing and establishing discussion of the study include effect of P-S interaction on consumer behavior, effects of promotion/selling on organizational performance, better persuasive ways to make good consumer marketing, innovative ways to create cohesive interaction modeling between P and S.

Literature reviews are hereby given in pursuing objective of study which circumscribes all the aspects by dividing into -

- *Consumer Perspective*
- *Organization Perspective*
- *Persuasion Perspective*

Consumer Perspective:

In this, the study is kept at the purview of consumer emphasis of about the interaction and its behavior by the demand and needs of consumer in the interaction.

Jean and Yazdanifard study (2015)^[7]: This study is an exploration to the field of consumer behavior by sales promotion activities. It has consulted with several research studies to arrive its objective conclusion of what the effects could be in all respects. This study has found that there is a strong relationship between sales promotion strategy and cognitive thinking and purchasing g behavior of consumer. It has also sighted the ways of make a profitable and sustainable sales promotion strategy. The ways include the price and quality intensive strategy, monetary strategy (monetary and non-monetary promotion strategy), brand reputation strategy, etc. There should be the serious awareness of entire marketing promotions during implementation of such strategy as obtained by the study - like, during low-price strategy, quality requires to be maintained. Also, non-monetary promotional sales strategy targets at functional products while the monetary strategy at entertainment products.

The study has given emphasis on the 'period' of sales promotion during which the consumer thinks and validates their (own) self-perception, personal well-being and mental satisfaction which entirely makes the purchase happen, in future, as they think benefited financially by the promotions during the period. Sayings of other consumers during the period, the consumers think as the feedback and it matters the part of the promotion effects also.

These findings are helpful and relate with the purpose of the study to determine with evaluation various facets of the interaction between promotion and selling.

Zhao et al. study (2020)^[13]: It is a study specific to the consumer segment in e-tail and mixed retail business supply chain market. The segment is peer-induced of fairness concern, so it is kind of niche marketing where it is observed the influence of the promotion (retailing on maximum) is significant on both of the consumer and the organization itself. Although there is the research needs of furtherance but it is also a field of concern by consumer involvement by degree as for any specific field to be concerned of. In order to gather better segmentation knowledge about the consumer this study is the one amongst and expected to be needful in the future marketing ahead.

Organization Perspective:

It has focused into by sales promotion and marketing.

Ajagbe, Long and Oluyinka study (2014)^[6]: It is the study which targets to establish the finding of the interaction of sales promotion with organization profitability. Branding is given included in the discussion to especially signify its effect of the organizational output. Chi-Square study is taken into its analysis by a questionnaire study made with the primary and secondary study. The study has obtained better co-relation of the interaction that the organization needs are better advanced and fulfilled by applying 'branding patronage' into the promotion.

Afande and Maina study (2015)^[8]: This study is quite different perspective to the discussion and gives to the advancement by the dimension in which term promotion mix includes elements such as sales promotion, advertising, personal selling and direct marketing. The study has described using SPSS study to determine the relation between the mix elements of organizational objectives. In doing this, the staffs of the mix elements in a financial organization were involved to get the finding. Lauter (1990) study has been suggested and given the study the perspective of 4P's with their corresponding 4 C's, like Customer solution (product), Customer cost (price), Convenience (place), Communication (promotion). Factors, the study emphasise in determining the objective, are target market, product life cycle, consumer's buying decision, production characteristics and channel features.

These factors and findings are quite of the confidence to proceed with the objective of the study at it recommends with various parallel thoughts of measure and suggestions like publicity, public relations.

Persuasion Perspective:

It is not possible to make entire coverage of 'persuasion' as a subject but to the subjective interest of the study some reviews are hereby given to pursuit of the research study as follows

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Friestad and Wright study (1994)^[1]: It is the study where the function 'persuasion' is discussed with the aim how to make the right, accurate and error-free decision in a persuasive consumer marketing. It becomes essential when the purchasing effort turns into a failure finally; then, the basis of trust of business becomes to be on the basis of persuasion by degree as applied through the marketing efforts. This is very crucial and not very easy purpose to penetrate through the consumer's purchasing persuasion correctly with effective endeavors.

There are various problems (like contamination by trait, belief system etc., erroneous advertisement, time-scale of persuasive effort, improper segmentation, etc.) of decision making on the promotion-selling interface about the consumer purchasing behavior, on the long-term, especially on the correct interactions of various persuasive efforts and reactions of consumers after initiated and experienced over them so discussed. Proper gluing is thereby essential in all kinds of interactions in the 'persuasive' consumer marketing.

The study has discussed various dimensions of how to make the correct marketing proposition through consumer persuasive intensions as traditional and contemporary also. Application of this study could make the study to better effectiveness and become competitively strategic.

O'Keefe study (2004)^[4]: This study has discussed the prospects in persuasion research. It suggests that there is the ability of the persuasion research to reach at the pinnacle of human behavioral study where the theory of attitude is not able to arrive at, because of generalization challenges, complexity in context-specific concepts, etc. Persuasion research is thereby an inevitable subject of discussion in making and creating the consumer research solutions fruitful and successful. The study, though, the qualitative one, is given with informative and knowledge enhancing one-one exemplary conversation which opens various unopened doors of the conception in order to have its necessity and implication mandatory and useful.

METHODOLOGY

In business marketing, it is always evident that behind any marketing proposition (product/service) there remains the fundamental applications and existence of business objective as desired by marketer. It is observed that marketers do not necessarily want their proposition to the 'rational sale' level than their persuasive presence in consumer's mind^[12]. Over the emergence of 'management' as the subject this is similarly true that marketers do take the philosophy of customer persuasion of selling on higher side than anything else, even just sales^[14]. They want to remain or reside in minds of consumer over long time period rather than just by one ('single' time!) selling/purchase. This is historical improvement/upgradation quite similar to service-giving approach to be more prominent than production approach (or selling) in now-a-days' business environment.

Significant marketing efforts are usually taken up by marketers. These efforts are marketing communications and others related to a marketing/business^[15]. In any effort of marketing/business management, usual channels taken by marketer usually include suitable media communication (print/digital), public awareness programme, different surveys (feedback/comment), etc^[16]. In all, as discussed, all the efforts at business/management objective in this study is said to be started from promotion (P) as described in Table 2 and Figure 5. As 'desired' results are S-based levels usually and affected through P's levels and other associated variables of promotion, so all outcomes of the cyclic process should remain at 'relative relational' level between S and other variables; suitable S as outcome could be possible by suitably applied 'involved' promotion variables. A maturity level at or a 'desired' S should mark an end of the cycle processes.

The two events, P and S, are thereby nonetheless the function of business management and do act individually with the interaction so happened in promotional marketing of business sales and as applicable in marketing proposition business^[16].

Model / Process Construction –

In marketing communication, no selling can ever happen without promotion – there would be always, even to a least count, an existence of promotional perception in consumers mind by purchase experience or brand recall. In order to keep up promotional existence as per organizational goals a marketer always tries such promotional program that should be an optimum to its selling or creation off selling; be it (promotion) short or long term.

Components of the model include -

- Node (starter node, intermediate node, end node)
- Nodal line
- Nodal variable (imaginary and assumed variable)
- Promotion levels by nodal line (that is promotion requirement by transformation stages)
- Δ level
- Sales curve

In the process model, nodes are given along with their’ inter-connecting paths which are called as nodal line. In Figure 6, given afterward, numerical 1 and 2 be nodes and their connecting path is denoted by arrow path. Direction is shown by direction of the arrow. Notably nodes are known as death or birth of cycle in transformation stages (Figure 5).

Figure 6: A typical connection of nodes and its connecting path

Considering a promotional program where promotion as a starter of the program acting to negotiate to selling of various intensities, Figure 7 gives the intensity-based sales over corresponding promotion levels where each transformation stage is defined by each separate line connecting between two nodes. For example, for a line between node 0 and node 1 the connected line is to be called as 0-1. There could be number of points or nodes in a marketing programme made by promotion (P).

Figure 7: Interaction diagram of sales-promotion (with transformation stages)

Length of each line by magnitude or value or else is dependent on several factors and these are like as the followings -

- Cost of promotion
- Attributes of promotion
- Time of promotion
- Emphasis (long term or short term) of promotion
- Organizational goals versus Financial budget
- Probable ‘leading’ attributes

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- Floating ‘selling’ strategy
- Others (market, competition, Porter's five forces, economic environment, life-cycle of proposition (product/service), changing ‘marketing’ environment, business strategy, technology, etc.)

As already discussed with the fact of transformation stages (Table 2 and Figure 5), there would be different promotional processes (by cycles) during cyclic process of promotion to selling. For multiple frequencies a sequentially continuous function of promotion and its processes to sales levels as a function of selling is valid.

Let, p = Promotion during ‘following’ stage of transformation process.

= promotion given by a marketing communication program.

p^* =Promotion during ‘leading’ stage of transformation.

= promotion yet to be required to reach at 'desired' sales.

Table 4: Description of marketing communication variables with actual reality

Promotion		Selling	
Transformation stage variable			
By Marketing Communication		By Sales Status	
+p	+p*	Assumed variable ($p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots$)	Imaginary variable (S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is related to ‘following’ stage. ▪ It connects to assumed variable by promotion degree/level/status (to preceding node of its acting promotion line). ▪ It is qualitative by nature. ▪ It is given by a marketing programme. ▪ It should always have a target to reach at ‘desired’ selling. ▪ Its intensity is influenced by the transformation of it. ▪ It has impact on determination of nodal variables (except starter nodal line) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is related to ‘leading’ stage. ▪ It connects to assumed variable by promotion degree/level/status (to preceding node of its acting promotion line). ▪ It is of qualitative by nature. ▪ It is given by a specific marketing programme. ▪ It should always have a target to reach at ‘desired’ selling. ▪ Its intensity is influenced by the transformation stage where it lies. ▪ It has impact on determination of nodal variables. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is always on right side of node. ▪ It is a functional output by p and p^*. ▪ For a nodal line (say 0-1, 1-2, 2-3... etc.) it is assumed that each node would include completely a new or accumulative value of the interaction requirement (by p) to negotiate and involve into the succeeding transformation process. ▪ It could be measured by quantity. ▪ It is cause of selling (that is imaginary variable). ▪ Including starter node, each node has this variable. ▪ It is named as ‘assumed’ as there is propositional variability as caused by market, demography, business strategy, economy and others. Due to the variability there is somewhat other magnitude (higher or lesser than p or p^*) of promotion that would be ‘actually’ acting to selling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is always on left side of node. ▪ It is a functional output by p and p^*. ▪ For any nodal line, there would be a rational output (in terms of s) by given promotion p^* as well as assumed promotion p. ▪ It could be measured by quantity. ▪ It is an effect of promotion (that is assumed variable). ▪ Except starter node, each node has this variable. ▪ It is denoted by ‘imaginary’ as the selling level could have better potential to reach at marketer’s desired level by strategy or else.

These two types of promotion (Figure 7) would be required by stages of transformation process so long as various factors as to decide on the promotional length are concerned to any marketing program.

Note: p and p^* to be always positive (+) and functional to accordingly, by a given promotion (marketing) strategy.

Table 5: Classification Of Node[^]

Name Of Node	Notation	Promotion Variable Type
Starter node	p_0	Assumed variable
End node	S	Imaginary variable
Intermediate node	p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots	Assumed variable
	s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots	Imaginary variable

[^]node is denoted by i and path by n as shown in Figure 7.

In Figure 7, transformation-stage specific promotions are shown alongwith nodes 0, 1, 2, 3, etc. As 0 the starter to interaction between promotion and selling, its subsequent nodes would be considered to be having an accumulative effect of promotion (p_0) of the starter node, although this might change to else by degree as needed. At each node there are two variables (except starter node) as formed or an effect by the interaction or transformation process. Say, for node 1, the two variables are p_1 (on right side) and s_1 (on left side) and in an interaction process, there is always an expectation that the process might provide the ‘desired’ selling. This selling which is denoted by the left-side variable at each node may be or may not be the ultimate sales planned by a marketing programme.

Henceforth the interaction process should be considered as a *continuous process function* with nodes of variables at each transformation as given by Table 1. It is thereby evident that at each node in the process there is a difference between level of selling and promotion.

Table 6: Nodal variable and its transformational functions

Promotion variable	Description	Positional feature
Imaginary	It is the variable obtained by summing up the preceding variable plus promotion-variable of the path connecting preceding node variable to the node of it.	At finish of any transformation stage
Assumed	It denotes demand of promotion needed at node position of it. Till a sufficient maturity to selling, transformation process always goes on with promotion variable, p and p^* , continuously and repeatedly, in the network progressively and this variable is always offered to and attached to the node position (of assumed type variable) every a time process continues to become into end stage of the transformation.	At start or beginning of any transformation stage

With not having a ‘desired’ selling, marketer always engages and involves the subsequent transformations (Table 2). For node 1, it is shown by p_1 which is required for ‘leading’ transformation stage to occur with the dissatisfaction to s_1 at node 1 (Figure 7).

Figure 8: Effect of Δ on sales by node level/magnitude

This promotional variable that is p_1 is expected to be *ultimately* (actually) acting on the selling effect to form s_2 for node 2 of promotion line 1-2, by p^* . So, right sided and left sided variables at each node are hereby termed as Assumed and Imaginary variable (Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6). This process continues by formation of these two variables by kinds at each node. Table 7 shows the description of variable formations at node level as well as node-line level. In this way of variables' demarcation the simple transformations have got into a system or process function (Figure 7 and Table 7). At all nodes except starter node and final or end node, there is a net effect on sales-promotion interaction. It is called as 'nodal net effect' (Δ) where relative presence of p and s exists (by their own degree of influence) together in a simultaneous manner. This relative existence is due to imaginary and assumed variable, indeed.

Table 7: Effect of transformation process on sales determination

Sl.	Node	Nodal line	Performance of promotion variable			Remarks
			Input given		Output obtained	
			Following	Leading		
1	0	0-1	p_0 (also by $+p$)	-	-	p_0 and p_1 by value to be decided and fixed by Table 4 and they should be with a precursor thought of $+p$ or $+p^*$ as applicable.
2	1		Output	-	s_1	
3	1	1-2	-	p_1 (by $+p_{1-2}^*$)	-	
4	2		-	output	s_2	

It is found and evident that with increase in sales level or promotion the net effect goes to decreasing magnitudes in itself (Table 8; Figure 8). This is node level. Later, it is discussed how dominance plays between p and s for a node or nodal path to derive its sales. Based on this, further simplification is done by plotting its profile on graphical representation (Figure 9) which is termed by "sales curve". By having centroidal position of sales curve, it is possible to find out the location (Y_c) of maximum difference of net effect (Δ) and the position (X_c) where maximum promotions are in existence.

For research interest let's assume a condition (of Δ) such that selling possibility by level as, $s_i > s_{i-1}$. Based on this, further simplification could be found out by plotting its profile on graphical representation (Figure 9) which is termed as *sales curve*. This sales curve shall have many more implications in the study as well.

Table 8: Δ (node point based) versus sales

Limiting value at node	Sales Level
Δ_1	s_1
Δ_2	s_2
Δ_3	s_3
...	...
Δ_{i-1}	s_{i-1}
Δ_i	s_i

As said the objective is to lay out a modelling construction of how a better balancing nature (by fundamental of course) of the interaction could be established by keeping related views and outcomes in visionary vantages, later on the sales curves have thereby been analyzed on a particular situational case where interaction profile we'd see (given afterwards in Figure 13, Figure 14).

Figure 9: Sales Curve (at each node) Of Promotional Activities

In Figure 9, by having centroidal position of sales curve, it is possible to find out the location (Y_c) of maximum difference of net effect (Δ) and the position (X_c) where maximum promotions are to be in the existence. Notably, A (along X axis) of Figure 9 could be summation of p and p^* .

Figure 10: Multiple Selling Curves (node-wise)

For given sales level there would be a specific sales curve as shown by Figure 9 which would be different (by geometric area or volume) by variety of levels of sales propositions and its effects. For i -th node, this way of enunciation would provide i -th number of curves as the sales curve. This uniqueness over all possible sales levels is shown in Figure 10 which proves the functional truthfulness of Figure 9 as by net effect, Δ , phenomenon (in the node-based sales).

Triangular area under sales curve could provide suitability to make flexible promotion as research interests. Intersection points of sales curves in Figure 10 denote the sales level position over variability as by 'given' promotions. Relative weightage of each promotion level, to such intersection) could thereby be recognized suitably so far as sales level is desired, to organizational goals, by similar intersection points of sales curves.

Now, say for node line 1-2 (Figure 7), at node 1, we've the following relation,

$$p_1 - s_1 \leq p_2 - s_2 \text{ [wherein, say, } s_i > s_{i-1}] \quad \dots \text{ (Eq. B)}$$

It is assuming that sales chance level increases with increasing promotion and decreasing Δ effect.

So, by applying net effect by node 1, $\Delta_1 = p_1 - s_1$.

and by node 2, $\Delta_2 = p_2 - s_2$.

Evidently, $\Delta_1 \leq \Delta_2$.

Thereby, $\Delta_i (= p_i - s_i) \leq \Delta_{i-1} (= p_{i-1} - s_{i-1})$.

Figure 11: Variables flow diagram (please see Figure 7)

Sales level at a given node (for node line 1-2) = promotion level (of preceding node + of connecting node-line).

So, by Figure 7, we get

For node 1, sales $s_1 = p_0 + p$

For node 2, sales $s_2 = p_1 + p^*$

So, for i-th node, $s_i = (p_{i-1})_{n-1} + (p_{n-1})_i \dots$ (Eq. 1)

It is additive in nature depending on respective sign by value so to be applied to the associated variables in Eq.1 (Figure 11). Suffixes n and i denote path-line and node point respectively. Table 9 gives notions to use of the variables.

Table 9: Notation used against variables[^]

Promotion variable	$(p_{i-1})_{n-1}$	$(p_{n-1})_i$	$(p_i)_n$	$(p_n^*)_{i+1}$
Notation	y1	x1	y2	x2
Variable type	Assumed	Transformation variable	Assumed	Transformation variable
Transformation type	Following (Forward)	Following (Forward)	Leading (Backward)	Leading (Backward)

[^]x: promotion. y: sales; variable of leading transformation type only carries star (*) sign as superscript for sake of understanding.

Again by Figure 7 (and Eq. B),

Sales level at a given node-path = imaginary variable magnitude (of the node-path) = variable (of assumed category + of connecting node-line) of succeeding path.

Thereby, for path 1, $s_1 \leq p_1 + (p^*)_{1-2}$

for path 2, $s_2 \leq p_2 + (p^*)_{2-3}$

So, for n-th path, $s_{n-1} \leq (p_i)_n + (p_n^*)_{i+1} \dots$ (Eq. 2)

Evidently, $s_i = s_{n-1} \dots$ (Eq. 3)

As selling level is assumed to be always growing and higher as promotion increases towards right direction of Figure 11, we've the following condition as, $s_{n-1} \leq s_n$

where, subjectively, $s_n = (p_i)_n + (p_n^*)_{i+1} \dots$ (Eq. 4)

Applying Eq.(1), Eq.(2), Eq.(3) and Eq.(4), $(p_{i-1})_{n-1} + (p_{n-1})_i \leq (p_i)_n + (p_n^*)_{i+1}$

It follows to,

$$\frac{(p_{i-1})_{n-1} + (p_{n-1})_i}{(p_i)_n + (p_n^*)_{i+1}} \leq 1$$

which furthers,

$$(p_{i-1})_{n-1} - (p_i)_n \leq +(p_n^*)_{i+1} - (p_{n-1})_i \dots \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

So far as variables function by their own features as described earlier, node-line variables (path variable) could also be determined similar to node point variables as described by Eq.5. Let's apply notation to get selling level expressions into simplification.

Figure 12.1: Positive sales

Figure 12.2: Negative sales

Figure 12: Positivity and negativity of sales

Applying Table 9, for the nodal discussions, and using Eq.5 we get,

$$\frac{x1 + y1}{x2 + y2} \leq 1$$

again simplifying, $x1 + y1 \leq x2 + y2$

which gives, $x2 - x1 \geq y1 - y2$

On the basis of above, hereby fifteen (15) conditions may be said out as determination interest as follows:

- As $x2 > x1$, so $y2 < y1$
- As $x2 > x1$, so $y2 = y1$
- As $x2 > x1$, so $y2 > y1$
- As $x2 < x1$, so $y2 > y1$
- As $x2 < x1$, so $y2 = y1$
- As $x2 < x1$, so $y2 < y1$
- As $x2 = x1$, so $y2 > y1$
- As $x2 = x1$, so $y2 = y1$
- As $x2 = x1$, so $y2 < y1$
- As $x1 = 0$; $x2 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 > y1$
- As $x1 = 0$; $x2 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 < y1$
- As $x1 = 0$; $x2 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 = y1$
- As $x2 = 0$; $x1 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 > y1$
- As $x2 = 0$; $x1 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 < y1$
- As $x2 = 0$; $x1 = \text{integer quantity}$, so $y2 = y1$

This way of relational attributes could be applied and derived with corresponding outcome of result. These conditions are of research interest and could be dealt with in upcoming researches.

Theoretical Study to Determine (Inter-) Dependency of Variables Functioning to Promotion and Sales in Business

However thereby continuing with earlier determination which is as, $x_2 - x_1 \geq -(y_2 - y_1) \dots$ (Eq. 6)

again, $x_1 - x_2 \leq y_2 - y_1$

thereby, $x_1 - x_2 \leq -(y_1 - y_2) \dots$ (Eq. 7)

Happening of sales is thereby described by Eq.(6) and Eq.(7) so long as their condition equations are satisfied so as to confer them to be exhibiting positivity and negativity into sales proposition respectively (Figure 12).

Table 10: Independent promotion levels

Level (L) of promotion	Total promotion
L1	10
L2	100
L3	1000
L4	10000
L5	100000

Final / End Sales (n-th level):

To determine final sales, let's sum up all the assumed and node-line variables (Figure 11), we get,

$$x_1 + y_1 + x_2 + y_2 + \dots + x_n + y_n = \text{Total promotional effect} = P_T \dots \text{(Eq. 8)}$$

Case 1. Equal / No Promotions -

Assumption: Assumed variable is not a part of node-line variable; assumed variables are of discreet nature and individually acting into sales.

Explanation: If there is equal promotion at each node-line upto n-th node path, we have following as,

$$x_1 + y_1 = x_2 + y_2 = \dots = x_n + y_n$$

Eq.(8) gives, $N(x_n + y_n) = P_T$

N = Total number of promotional effects or promotions.

So, $(x_n + y_n) = \frac{P_T}{N} \dots \text{(Eq. 9)}$

If it is assumed P_T as unity, then $(x_n + y_n) = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)$

We could now draw out and determine final sales profile using an assumed set of values of promotion by using Eq.(9).

Table 11: Sales Versus Promotion

Level of promotion (unit)	Final sales (S), unit									
	N1 (N=0.1)	N2 (N=0.2)	N3 (N=0.3)	N4 (N=0.4)	N5 (N=0.5)	N6 (N=0.6)	N7 (N=0.7)	N8 (N=0.8)	N9 (N=0.9)	N10 (N=1.0)
L1	100	50	33	25	20	17	14	13	11	10
L2	1000	500	333	250	200	167	143	125	111	100
L3	10000	5000	3333	2500	2000	1667	1429	1250	1111	1000
L4	100000	50000	33333	25000	20000	16667	14286	12500	11111	10000
L5	1000000	500000	333333	250000	200000	166667	142857	125000	111111	100000

Let's consider values against promotion by its different levels L1, L2, etc. and Table 10 is the one of the consideration that could be applicable to any marketing programme by advertising, media communication and such.

Using Table 10, different sales levels at different suitably selected N values are determined as given in Table 11. Final sales values (at various N sets) are then converted to the determinations like Weighted Average Sales (W.A.S), Average Sales (A.S) and Difference (W.A.S minus A.S).

This conversion is likely to obtain an integrated effect as entire representation against each promotion level (Table 12) of a promotion programme in business management. All these then are given with best fit curve enunciation to plot out the sales profiles (as given in Table 13 and Table 14 respectively for Figure 13 and Figure 14). These profiles lead to establish the finding to determine an interaction model that could deliver anticipated results, based on considered category of levels as described. Thereby, profile findings would act as a pathway of future research and forecasting sales models for given promotion levels associated with N. For a paradigm analysis, it can be said that the analysis of the 'base' profiles would go with nature of best-fit taken into consideration.

For information, linear best-fits are found to be on and along or same as original base curve (base curves marked by markers while trend curves marked by without markers). Say, difference magnitude of 27.19 is 10 times lower than promotion level of 1,00,000 unit (Table 13 and Table 14). This illustration gives distinction of use and scope of research onwards sales level output as per given promotion levels.

Table 12: Analysis[^] of sales determination

Level of promotion	Weighted Average Sales (W.A.S), unit	Average Sales (A.S), unit	Difference (=W.A.S - A.S.), unit
L1	18	29	11
L2	182	293	111
L3	1818	2929	1111
L4	18182	29290	11108
L5	181818	292897	111079

[^]S1 = sales at N1 and so on; W.A.S = (N1S1+N2S2+. . .) divided by (N1+N2+...); A.S = (S1+S2+. . .) divided by (N1+N2+...).

Table 10 to Table 12 are self-explanatory to the (assumed) levels of P and S so determined (where each P and S to be unit quantity that may be expressed in any quantity; be S as final sales acquired in money or output volume as against money expended in P in terms of multiplication value or money or else as applicable. Like this, Table 13 and Table 14 are also self-expressive, giving the profile in a mathematical version. So, by changing N-value, lots of scopes are there to originate and determine the pattern, profile and their modelling presentation.

It is evident from the profiles that sales level could provide the flexibility to make a promotion to be able to equip with several marketing factorials as suitably possible to be applicable in a business market scenario. Comparative view between W.A.S and A.S has shown the better significance (for given N values' benchmarking) of this flexible applicability and scope of use. We can also write for the case as assumption of the case itself that Total promotion = Final selling (s_n); so Eq.(9) comes as, $s_n = (x_n + y_n) = \frac{P_T}{N} \dots$ (Eq. 10)

To make sales profitable, there needs to be $N \geq 1$; preferable between 0 and 1 for N. It is given by profile in Figure 13 and Table 10 wherein profile trends are determined by excel programming. It is thereby clear that Eq.10 describes the condition of no promotion ever (or yet to be given) or equal promotion magnitude at all nodes. In this note, it is to mention Figure 10 to identify promotional sales of equal nature.

Case 2. Non-Equal Promotions -

Sales level could be determined so discussed well upto Figure 10, also in suitable combination with upto Figure 12. Assumptions of Case 1 shall be unchanged in this case also.

Table 13: Profile of total promotions against final sales levels (sales = 1,000 times total promotions)

Profile		Profile determination (y:sales; x:total promotion)		
		Weighted Average Sales (W.A.S)	Average Sales (A.S)	Difference [^]
Linear Profile (without intercept set at 0.0)	Equation	$y = 1.818x$	$y = 2.929x - 5E-14$	$y = 1.110x + 8E-14$
	R ² value	$R^2 = 1$	$R^2 = 1$	$R^2 = 1$
Exponential Profile (without intercept set at 0.0)	Equation	$y = 44.51e^{0.003x}$	$y = 71.71e^{0.003x}$	$y = 27.19e^{0.003x}$
	R ² value	$R^2 = 0.817$	$R^2 = 0.817$	$R^2 = 0.817$

[^]difference = W.A.S minus A.S; y=sales (final) by level; x=promotion by unit level.

Case 3. Part of Promotions -

Assumption:

Assumed variable is a part of node-line variable and vice-versa ($p < p^*$ and also, $p < p^*$).

Explanation:

Total promotion is given by as, $P_T = (x_1 + y_1 + x_2 + y_2 + \dots + x_n + y_n)$.

Let, $x_1 = f_1 y_1$; where f = factorization (=f₁ for set of x₁ and y₁ variable as shown in Figure 11).

Then, $P_T = y_1(1 + f_1) + y_2(1 + f_2) + y_3(1 + f_3) + \dots + y_n(1 + f_n)$.

By the case 3 so concerned (that is $p < p^*$ and also $p < p^*$), we have the following condition of f value as, $f_1 > 1$ for $x_1 < y_1$; $f_1 < 1$ for $x_1 > y_1$.

So, $P_T = (y_1 + y_2 + y_3 + \dots + y_n) + [(y_1 f_1) + (y_2 f_2) + (y_3 f_3) + \dots + (y_n f_n)] \dots$ (Eq. 11)

Table 14: Profile of total promotions against final sales levels (sales = 1,00,000 times total promotions)

Profile		Profile determination (y:sales; x:promotion)		
		Weighted Average Sales (W.A.S)	Average Sales (A.S)	Difference [^]
Linear Profile (without intercept set at origin 0.0)	Equation	$y = 1.818x + 4E-12$	$y = 2.929x - 5E-12$	$y = 1.110x + 4E-12$
	R ² value	$R^2 = 1$	$R^2 = 1$	$R^2 = 1$
Exponential Profile	Equation	$y = 445.1e^{6E-05x}$	$y = 717.1e^{6E-05x}$	$y = 271.9e^{6E-05x}$
	R ² value	$R^2 = 0.577$	$R^2 = 0.577$	$R^2 = 0.577$

[^]difference = W.A.S - A.S; x and y as shown in Figure 14.

If f value is same for all the variables, then $P_T = 2(y_1 + y_2 + y_3 + \dots + y_n)$ that is able to determine the sales level.

The repetitive nature of the process is clearly seen by the functional series form as obtained in Eq.11. It is hereby proved that Eq.(11) shows and comes out as the application outlet of Fourier series to get used of, so far as continuous nature of transformation stages (Figure 5) exists in promotion-selling interaction, leading to evaluate the process broadly by significant control and accuracy. So, Fourier series application could be this study's future scope of research as well.

Figure 13: Final Sales Profile (Upto P=1000 unit)

With all these determinations, promotion interaction to sales by levels is thereby found with its ultimatum and desirableness as ‘to be’ decided by a marketer in his/her marketing programme, definitely as envisaged by Figure 1 as its basis and by its boundaries as fundamental. From these, sales level function alongwith promotion interactions could be better viewed and controlled by levels of P’s (where, in all interactions, P is taken as independent and S as dependent variable). With this study, all core levels (in P as well as S) would extend itself to its boundary limits (PPB and SPB as shown in Figure 1) by the findings so obtained and determined in this study.

Relational relativeness between P and S or S and P for attaining numerous pairing levels (of ‘repeatedly’ continuity interest) by interaction (by own individual definition of variability of P and S) could thereby be provided in order to create, spread and establish a good and balanced synergy model of P-S interaction and media effectiveness measurability in marketing business.

Figure 14: Final Sales Profile (Upto P=1,00,000 unit)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following extractions are found as followed -

- Interaction presentation by node-based layout gives the insight concepts that help to build up stronger knowledge and applications in *sales prominence*.
- Difference of promotion requirements by transformation processes provides *differentiative* applications to reach to the sales curve that is a remarkable outcome of the study.

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- Given in recommendation (discussed afterwards), various products/services would be possible to be designed based on categorical type like obedient, righteous, etc. Promotion by its levels thereby becomes a function of *proposition formation* or determination for it.
- It (the study) could act as a readily available tool (as model) to marketer to act on in market with right promotion *interaction decision*.

Figure 15: P-S interaction outcomes, leading to ‘product’ propositions – physical ‘producing’

- Application by Fourier series is valid reasonably as the transformation process is *repetitive and continuous*. So, it is possible to describe limitation of an interaction to achieve a ‘desired’ sales level.
It is also found that an interaction function subjected to no further promotions would be having the sales level immediately at the succeeding nodal position (imaginary variable) of the subjected nodal line.
- Enunciation of *methodological sales curve* by net effect at node is to be a pathway to further scope to research improvements.
Areal measurements alongwith *centroidal determination of sales curve* (node-wise) would give potential strength of the promotion to cause to the nodal sales level.

CONCLUSIONS

The study can be concluded with followings as followed -

- Drive of promotion to lead to discover more new segments in a proposition and market both.
- Marketer would facilitate promotions as per their own choice and decision making, depending on nodal net effects.
- Less sales is not bad, unless it is examined on the net nodal effect by contributory potential that the proposition has with respect to consumer and market demography by country economy.
- Sales level determination for a given promotion by level is an image to promotion level determination for a given sales level and it’s also vice-versa. Nonetheless promotion is to be always a function of ‘desired’ sales level.
- Entire discussion is discriminated by methodological research by taking consideration of a difference between node-line promotions and at-node promotional improvements.
- Leading than Following transformation is considered to be more driving and result-giving.
- Starter node implies to promotion while end node to a sales level.
- Less cycles (of transformation process) would be required if expertise in hand. More in number of cycles would provide a better stage of potentiality utilization and sharpening competitive edge.
- Relative comparison among a set of sales-levels gives basis of determining ‘profitable’ and ‘reasonable’ interaction requirement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Followings may be considered as forthcoming aspects of the study -

- 1) Based on interaction descriptions and findings, there could be four interaction outcomes that should be prevailing in on an interaction between P and S (given in Figure 15). The four outcomes, namely, Risky, Obedient, Righteous, Obvious, are completely theoretical till now, as it has been derived out by applying logical reasoning among the four on the status. Interaction discussions so far as described herein are all to be subjected to these four outcomes. That means, outcomes which do signify a type and feature by nature, quality, etc. of a proposition would satisfy to be valid to all findings of the study as well.
- 2) Also, there is in the four outcomes existing a value/perspective similarity and with such similarity following pairs are possible and would be of ‘apparently conjugative’ type to each other in each pair:
 - ✓ Obvious equivalent to Righteous.
 - ✓ Risky equivalent to Obedient.
- 3) This outcome may be termed as ‘physical producing’ of the interaction. Each pair and its similarity (Figure 15) would give knowledge of proclivity or tending increase pattern and direction among four outcomes of proposition character as shown by Figure 15. This phenomenon is rational because of marketing nature and variability of marketing functions, mix elements, etc. so far as to the need fulfillment criterion of marketing objective to a marketer.
- 4) As process function is continuous so the function forms a sequential function of series nature. This series nature the study has considered to proclaim it as a Fourier series function mathematically. Any limited margin of the continuous ‘Fourier’ function is to be either any given quantity or infinity by level is to be as required – this all to be depending on satisfactory level of interaction between promotion and selling. So, a starter node or final node shall have all this to finalize about a continuous Fourier series nature of the interaction in an entire promotion process. Nonetheless to say again, end node variable is to be an imaginary variable till its completed validation by satisfaction.
- 5) Application of WAS and AS concept is found to be a correct one to determine value to as accurate as possible. Determination of ‘difference’ also implies the same objective. Moreover Table 11 and Table 12 show that its row-wise findings mean to the determination status of sales levels by promotion’s level-wise manner.

By same way it could be done for column-wise value determinations – it could have been found by the similar way and that would indicate effect on sales levels by various N-levels. So, we could obtain this methodological way of findings and get perspective view of the effects by concerned changes and corresponding fundamental bases.
- 6) Centroidal determination of a sales curve (Figure 9) is another facet of the study to signify its related importance to marketing business pursuits.
- 7) Finally, not the last one, the study could be able to create promotion model as it has the output like sales curves, Fourier series implication, best-fit curve formulations etc.

Further research study should be taken to the fore in its next research level where validation of sales level would be described in order to check and verify the data of sales as poured out by the model itself so determined by this present study of fundamental interest to any kind of promotion in business management.

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